

Simulation Algorithm

Theoretical background

Here will introduce the reader to the methods for the simulations performed in the article. The main difficulty in the simulation relative to other standard methods such as the classical Gillespie's algorithm is that the processes occur at state-dependent propensities and evolve dynamically along time.

Consider that we define the timer τ as $\frac{d\tau}{dt} = 1$ and it is reset $\tau \rightarrow 0$ every time a reaction occurs. If x_0 is the protein concentration just after the most recent reaction, consider a hybrid process that, in between discrete jumps, evolves with the ordinary differential equation:

$$\frac{dx(\tau)}{d\tau} = g(x), \quad x|_{\tau=0} = x_0. \quad (1)$$

In our particular case, time evolution consists of continuous protein dilution at a rate $\gamma(x)x$. Thus, $g(x) = -\gamma(x)x$.

Let us say that we want to simulate the time of occurrence of a jump process with propensity $f(x)$, this can be either the protein synthesis with a state-dependent propensity or a division event. As explained in Fig. 1 We use $P_0(\tau)$ to represent the probability that the selected cell has not undergone the reaction during the time interval $(0, \tau)$, while $P_1(\tau)$ signifies the probability that the reaction occurs during the time interval $(0, \tau)$. With a given reaction rate $f(x)$, we are able to formulate the Master equation as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dP_1(\tau)}{d\tau} &= f(x(\tau))P_0(\tau) \\ &= f(x(\tau))(1 - P_1(\tau)), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where we used $P_0 + P_1 = 1$. Upon rearranging Equation (2) and integrating both sides, we obtain

$$-\ln(1 - P_1(\tau)) = \int_0^\tau f(x(u))du. \quad (3)$$

To generate the reaction time τ_r we generate a random number $r \sim U(0, 1)$, uniformly distributed in the interval $(0, 1)$, the instant of time τ_r defined as the time when the reaction occurs,

Schematic diagram:

Figure 1: **The scheme of the method to determine reaction time.** A reaction can be simplified as a single step process with a non-homogeneous (state-dependent) rate of occurrence $f(x)$. The state continuously evolves following the differential equation $\frac{dx}{dt} = g(x)$.

Table 1: **Formulas used in the simulation algorithm.** For each mechanism, in the simulation, we consider the protein concentration x following a dynamics given by each differential equation. Given the protein concentration x_0 just after the previous reaction, the time to synthesis τ_s and time to division τ_d are estimated from a random number r uniformly distributed in $(0, 1)$.

Var.	Unregulated	Reg. Synthesis	Reg. Dilution
$x(\tau)$	$\frac{dx}{d\tau} = -x$ $x(\tau) = x_0 e^{-\tau}$	$\frac{dx}{d\tau} = -x$ $x(\tau) = x_0 e^{-\tau}$	$\frac{dx}{d\tau} = -x^2$ $x(\tau) = \frac{x_0}{1+x_0\tau}$
τ_s	$-\frac{1}{k_x} \ln(r)$	$\ln\left(1 - \left[\frac{x_0}{k_x}\right] \ln(r)\right)$	$-\frac{1}{k_x} \ln(r)$
τ_d	$-\ln(r)$	$-\ln(r)$	$\frac{1}{x_0} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) - 1\right]$

can be estimated from r by solving the following equation:

$$\tau_r = \left\{ \tau : -\ln(r) = \int_0^\tau f(x(u))du, \quad x|_{u=0} = x_0 \right\}, \quad (4)$$

with the initial condition $x(t_0) = x_0$. In Table I, we explain the solution of (4) for different reactions (protein synthesis and division) depending on the particular protein dynamics of the gene expression mechanism.

Algorithm 1 presents a schematic implementation of the simulation algorithm. After each reaction (either protein synthesis or cell division), we estimate the time to next protein synthesis τ_s and the time to division τ_d based on the state just after the reaction x_0 . We select the minimum of both times as the reaction time. During the time interval to this reaction time, we evolve the state (1) and then implement the reaction. We repeat this procedure until the time to the next reaction is greater than the time T we want to finish the simulation. In that case, we evolve the state by solving (1) again until T . This T can be associated not only with the end of the simulation but also with the time to data export if the goal of the simulation is to plot the protein trajectory.

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Data:  $x|_{t=0} = x_0, k_x, T, B_x$ 
Result:  $x|_{t=T}$ 
 $x = x_0, \tau' = 0;$ 
 $r_1 = \text{random}(0, 1), \tau_1 = \tau_s(r_1);$ 
 $r_2 = \text{random}(0, 1), \tau_2 = \tau_d(r_2);$ 
 $\tau_{min} = \min(\tau_1, \tau_2);$ 
 $\tau = \tau_{min};$ 
if  $\tau > T$  then
  |  $x|_{t=T} = \int_0^T g(u)du;$ 
else
  | while  $\tau < T$  do
  | |  $x = \int_0^{\tau-\tau'} g(u)du;$ 
  | | if  $\tau_{min} == \tau_1$  then
  | | |  $B \sim \text{Exponential}(B_x);$ 
  | | |  $x = x + B;$ 
  | | else
  | | | Divide Cell
  | | end
  | |  $r_1 = \text{random}(0, 1), \tau_1 = \tau_s(r_1);$ 
  | |  $r_2 = \text{random}(0, 1), \tau_2 = \tau_d(r_2);$ 
  | |  $\tau_{min} = \min(\tau_1, \tau_2);$ 
  | |  $\tau' = \tau;$ 
  | |  $\tau = \tau + \tau_{min};$ 
  | end
  |  $x|_{t=T} = \int_{\tau'}^T g(u)du;$ 
end

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Algorithm 1: Given the initial protein concentration x_0 , the time to complete the simulation T and the reaction parameters k_x, B_x , explained in the main text, we obtain the protein concentration at the end of the simulation $x|_{t=T}$.